

Interview Guide

Part 1 – Introduction

Interviewer introduces the goal of the study (integrating chatbots in development process), and asks the participant for consent to record the interview.

Part 2 – Background and demographics

Participants briefly describe their background. The company they work for, their role, years of experience, team size and responsibilities.

Part 3 – State of practice (10 min)

1. Do you use chatbots in your organization?
 - If yes:
 - What chatbots?
 - For what purpose?
 - Do you have any license?
 - Any policies regarding their use?
 - If no:
 - Are you planning on using them?
 - If yes, ... (similar set to previous alternative)
2. What would influence your company's **decision** to adopt into your process?
 - Research? Expert opinion? Examples of successful adoption? Developer's productivity?
 - Would that decision be influenced if competitors are using them?
3. What would you find appropriate to use chatbots for in your company? What use cases or scenarios would you not be open to use them?

Part 3 – Concerns about chatbot adoption (10 min)

4. What are your main **concerns** when it comes to integrating chatbots in the development process?
5. To what extent do you feel that you need to be transparent about using them to the customers or the public?
 - Would this impact your company's reputation in any way?

Part 4 – Actions to integrate (10 min)

6. What kind of **organizational changes** are required for adopting LLMs in the development process?
 - What kind of approvals do you need? Do you need to show evidence of chatbot benefits?
7. How will your policies change? Will you need to create new ones?
8. How will maintenance look like for these chatbots? Will there be a need to introduce new roles in the company?